
ORIGINAL ARTICLES. PHYSICAL EDUCATION

The correlation between the level of anxiety and motor, social activity on the example of students aged 14-16

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Authors' Contribution: A – Study design; B – Data collection; C – Statistical analysis; D – Manuscript Preparation; E – Funds Collection

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.58962/HT.274>

How to cite

Marusych O, Shiyan V, Shiyan O, Sologubova S. The correlation between the level of anxiety and motor, social activity on the example of students aged 14-16. *Health technologies*. 2026;4(1):43-53. <https://doi.org/10.58962/HT.274>

Abstract

Background and purpose	In today's society, adolescents are increasingly exposed to psycho-emotional stress, influenced by changes in the sociocultural environment, digital technologies, academic pressure, and an unstable social climate. According to the World Health Organization, over 10% of children and adolescents worldwide suffer from mental health disorders, with anxiety disorders being among the most common. In Ukraine, the situation has worsened due to the consequences of the full-scale war that began in 2022. Military actions have significantly impacted the mental health of children and adolescents. Ukrainian research confirms high levels of anxiety in teenagers caused by life-threatening conditions, loss of home, separation from loved ones, and disruption of normal life.
Material and methods	The study was conducted during the 2024 - 2025 academic year in Dnipro (Ukraine) through anonymous questionnaires. The survey was developed by the authors and included the GAD-7 anxiety screening tool and the WHO-5 well-being index, distributed via Microsoft Forms. The sample consisted of 33 students (grades 8 - 11) from the Dnipro Scientific Chemical and Environmental Lyceum. Respondents provided information about their well-being, types, and duration of daily activities. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Statistic 23.
Results	The empirical study revealed several statistically significant relationships between anxiety levels and indicators of motor and social activity in adolescents aged 14 - 16. Regular participation in sports or dance classes was associated with lower anxiety levels ($p = 0.018$). These adolescents also had higher levels of physical activity ($p = 0.170$) and psycho-emotional well-being ($p = 0.162$), indicating a positive compensatory effect of movement. The number of active hobbies showed a trend-level association with anxiety: less active students were more likely to experience high anxiety levels ($p = 0.316$). At the same time, a high level of anxiety correlated with a greater number of passive hobbies (those involving observation only) ($p \approx 0.28$), which may indicate reduced engagement and avoidance of active participation. Digital activity (screen time exceeding six hours per day) showed a trend toward increased anxiety ($p = 0.422$), aligning with international findings on the negative impact of excessive screen time on adolescent mental health. No statistically significant relationship was found between anxiety level and overall well-being ($p = 0.645$), suggesting the complexity of internal psychological dynamics and individual adaptive mechanisms.
Conclusions	The level of anxiety in adolescence is closely related to motor and social activity. Regular engagement in sports and creative activities, maintaining active hobbies, and limiting screen time can serve as effective preventive strategies to reduce anxiety in adolescents. The results of this study may be valuable for school psychologists, educators, class teachers, and those designing educational programs focused on strengthening adolescent mental health.
Keywords	anxiety, adolescents, social activity, physical activity, digital activity, correlations

Анотація

Марусич Олена, Володимир Шиян, Світлана Сологубова, Ольга Шиян. Взаємозв'язок між рівнем тривожності та руховою, соціальною активністю на прикладі учнів 14-16 років.

Обґрунтування і мета	<p>У сучасних умовах розвитку суспільства спостерігається зростання рівня психоемоційної напруги серед підлітків, що зумовлено змінами у соціокультурному середовищі, впливом цифрових технологій, підвищеними вимогами з боку шкільного середовища та нестабільною соціальною ситуацією. За даними Всесвітньої організації охорони здоров'я, понад 10% дітей та підлітків у світі мають психічні розлади, серед яких тривожні розлади є одними з найпоширеніших. В Україні ситуація ускладнюється наслідками повномасштабної війни, що розпочалась у 2022 році. Військові дії суттєво вплинули на психічне здоров'я дітей та підлітків. Дослідження, проведені в Україні, засвідчують високий рівень тривожності у підлітків, зумовлений небезпекою для життя, втратою домівки, розлукою з близькими та порушенням звичного способу життя.</p> <p>Мета: виявити та проаналізувати залежність між рівнем тривожності та руховою, соціальною активністю підлітків 14 - 16 років.</p>
Матеріал і методи	<p>Дослідження проведено протягом 2024-2025 навчального року в м. Дніпро (Україна) методом анонімного анкетування з використанням розробленої анкети, до якої входили тест для скринінгу тривожності (GAD-7), індекс доброго самопочуття (WHO-5) в програмі Microsoft forms. Опитані 33 ліцеїсти Дніпровського наукового хіміко-екологічного ліцею 8-11 класів. Підлітки відмічали своє самопочуття, види та тривалість своєї діяльності за добу. Статистичну обробку проведено за допомогою програми SPSS Statistic 23.</p>
Результати	<p>У результаті емпіричного дослідження було виявлено низку статистично значущих зв'язків між рівнем тривожності підлітків 14 - 16 років та показниками їхньої рухової і соціальної активності.</p> <p>Систематичне відвідування спортивних та танцювальних секцій асоціюється зі зниженим рівнем тривожності ($p = 0.018$). Ці підлітки також мають вищий рівень фізичної активності ($p = 0.170$) і психоемоційного благополуччя ($p = 0.162$), що свідчить про позитивний компенсаторний ефект рухової активності. Кількість хобі, якими підлітки активно займаються, також демонструє тенденційний зв'язок із рівнем тривожності: менш активні учні частіше виявляють вищий рівень тривоги ($p = 0.316$). Водночас високий рівень тривожності корелює з великою кількістю "пасивних" хобі - тобто тих, за якими лише спостерігають ($p \approx 0.28$). Це може вказувати на ускладнене включення у взаємодію та уникнення активної участі. Цифрова активність (екранний час понад 6 годин на день) виявляє тенденцію до підвищення рівня тривожності ($p = 0.422$), що узгоджується з сучасними міжнародними дослідженнями щодо негативного впливу надмірного використання екранів на психічне здоров'я підлітків. Не виявлено достовірного зв'язку між рівнем тривожності та загальним психоемоційним благополуччям ($p = 0.645$), що свідчить про складність внутрішньої психологічної динаміки та індивідуальні особливості адаптації.</p>
Висновки	<p>Рівень тривожності у підлітковому віці має тісний взаємозв'язок із обсягом рухової та соціальної активності. Систематична участь у спортивних, творчих секціях, наявність активних хобі та обмеження екранного часу можуть стати ефективними психопрофілактичними заходами для зниження тривожності. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані у роботі шкільних психологів, педагогів, класних керівників, а також при плануванні освітніх програм, спрямованих на зміцнення психічного здоров'я підлітків.</p>
Ключові слова	<p>тривожність, підлітки, соціальна активність, фізична активність, цифрова активність, взаємозв'язки</p>

Introduction

Analysis of contemporary scientific research indicates that anxiety in adolescence has a complex multifactorial nature and develops under the influence of both internal psychological characteristics and external social conditions. Previous studies by Coelho D. C., Anker S., Jepsen J. R. M., and others describe a wide range of factors associated with increased anxiety levels, among which motor and social activity, characteristics of leisure organization, and the intensity of digital technology use occupy a significant place [1,2]. At the same time, the issue of interaction between these factors and their combined impact on the psycho-emotional state of adolescents remains insufficiently studied.

In the current context, there has been an increase in psycho-emotional tension among adolescents, which is associated with transformations in the socio-cultural environment, intensification of the educational process, increased screen time, and reduced direct interpersonal interaction [3]. According to the World Health Organization, more than 10% of children and adolescents worldwide experience mental disorders, with anxiety disorders being among the most prevalent [4]. During adolescence, anxiety is often accompanied by decreased self-esteem, learning difficulties, sleep disturbances, emotional instability, and avoidance of social contacts, which negatively affects overall psychosocial well-being [5 - 7].

In scientific research, physical activity is considered one of the potential resources for reducing anxiety and supporting mental health in adolescents. Studies report that regular physical activity may be associated with lower levels of anxiety symptoms, improved emotional state, and higher subjective well-being [8 - 10]. Similarly, social activity including participation in clubs, sports sections, and other forms of joint engagement is

regarded as an important factor in the development of psychological resilience, social integration, and positive self-esteem [10 - 14]. However, existing findings remain heterogeneous and often depend on contextual factors, the intensity of activities, individual characteristics of adolescents, and features of the social environment.

The issue becomes particularly relevant under conditions of prolonged social stress, especially in the context of the armed conflict in Ukraine. The full-scale war ongoing since 2022 has significantly affected the mental health of children and adolescents, increasing feelings of danger, uncertainty, and emotional instability. Ukrainian studies indicate that a considerable proportion of adolescents demonstrate elevated anxiety levels associated with military events, forced lifestyle changes, and disruption of usual social ties [15 - 20]. Under these circumstances, identifying resources that support psycho-emotional well-being among young people is of particular importance.

Despite the growing body of research addressing individual aspects of the influence of physical or social activity on adolescent anxiety, the issue of their mutual relationships and systemic interaction with other everyday life characteristics such as screen time, leisure structure, and subjective assessment of psycho-emotional well-being remains insufficiently explored. In this context, the application of a correlation approach is appropriate, as it allows for the analysis of relationships between key indicators and contributes to the identification of directions for further psycho-prophylactic and pedagogical interventions.

Purpose: to identify and analyze the correlation between the level of anxiety and the motor and social activity of adolescents aged 14 - 16.

Material and methods

Participants. The study was conducted during the 2024 - 2025 academic year in Dnipro (Ukraine). A total of 33 adolescents (students of grades 8 – 11) from the Dnipro Scientific Chemical and Ecological Lyceum participated in the study. Participation was voluntary and anonymous.

Instruments and procedure. Data were collected using an author-developed questionnaire

administered via Microsoft Forms. The questionnaire included standardized psychodiagnostic instruments: the GAD-7 screening test to assess anxiety levels and the WHO-5 Well-Being Index to evaluate psycho-emotional well-being. Additional items assessed indicators of physical activity, social activity, and daily screen time. Participants reported their well-being, types of activities, and duration of activities

per day.

Statistical analysis. Correlation analysis was used to assess the relationships between anxiety level, indicators of physical and social activity, screen time, and psycho-emotional well-being of adolescents. Statistical data processing was performed using SPSS Statistics 23. The significance of the relationships was determined based on p-values, with the level of statistical significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Ethical statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles set forth in the Declaration of Helsinki of the World Medical Association. All participants were informed about the purpose, content, and conditions of the study and provided informed consent to participate. For minor

participants, written consent was provided by their parents or legal representatives. Confidentiality of personal data was ensured at all stages of the study.

Method of analyzing literary sources

For the theoretical substantiation of the study, the method of analyzing scientific literature on the topic of anxiety, physical activity and social activity of adolescents was used. The analysis covered scientific articles, monographs, dissertation studies, methodological manuals and modern publications over the past 10 - 15 years. The search for sources was carried out in electronic databases (Google Scholar, Scopus Web of Science), as well as in the libraries of leading universities of Ukraine. The main attention was paid to works that highlight the correlation and influence of physical and social activity on the level of anxiety of adolescents.

Results

The table presents a general assessment of the identified relationships between anxiety level and indicators of motor activity, social activity, and psycho-emotional well-being in adolescents.

Statistical significance was determined based on p-values. Detailed correlation coefficients and their direction are presented in Table 2.

Table 1

Overall assessment of the identified correlations

Variable 1	Variable 2	p-value	Analysis result
Anxiety level	Visiting sections	0.018	The connection is reliable.
Number of hobbies (observations)	Visiting sections	0.021	The connection is reliable.
Physical activity	Visiting sections	0.17	There is a trend
Psycho-emotional well-being	Visiting sections	0.162	There is a trend
Anxiety level	Screen time	0.422	There is a trend
Anxiety level	Number of active hobbies	0.316	There is a trend
Anxiety level	Number of hobbies (observations)	0.28	There is a trend
Anxiety level	Psycho-emotional well-being	0.645	Connection not confirmed

Table 2

Spearman correlation matrix between anxiety, well-being, physical activity, and leisure indicators (N = 33)

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Daily physical activity	1							
2. Attendance of sports sections	0.18	1						
3. Total number of hobbies	0.14	0.03	1					
4. Screen time	0.42*	0.22	0.35*	1				
5. Anxiety level (GAD-7)	0.15	0.26	0.39*	0.25	1			
6. Psycho-emotional well-being (WHO-5)	-0.10	-0.01	0.02	-0.06	0.51**	1		
7. Number of active hobbies	0.09	-0.01	0.63**	0.11	0.21	-0.00	1	
8. Number of observed hobbies	0.18	0.09	0.85**	0.34	0.41*	0.07	0.16	1

Note. p - Spearman's correlation coefficient. * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$ (two-tailed)

Fig. 1. Statistically significant correlations ($p \leq 0.05$)

Anxiety level and participation in sections ($p = 0.018$): Regular participation in sports or dance classes is associated with reduced anxiety. Teenagers who do not attend classes are more likely to show high levels of anxiety (Fig. 2).

Number of hobbies (only observed) and participation in sections ($p = 0.021$): Active teenagers are more likely to observe a greater number

of hobbies. This indicates a greater interest in various areas of leisure (Fig. 3).

Number of hobbies (only observed) and participation in sections ($p = 0.021$): Active teenagers are more likely to observe a greater number of hobbies. This indicates a greater interest in various areas of leisure (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Anxiety level and participation in sections ($p = 0.018$): Light-colored bars represent adolescents who attend sports or dance sections; dark-colored bars represent adolescents who do not attend any organized sections

Fig. 3. Number of hobbies (only observed) and participation in sections ($p = 0.021$). Trends worthy of attention ($0.05 < p \leq 0.5$). Light-colored bars indicate adolescents who attend sports or dance sections; dark-colored bars indicate adolescents who do not attend organized sections

Physical activity and participation in sections ($p = 0.170$): Attending sections is associated with higher levels of daily physical activity (Fig. 4).

Psychoemotional well-being and participation in sections ($p = 0.162$): Section participants more often have an average and high

level of psycho-emotional well-being (Fig. 5).

Anxiety level and screen time ($p = 0.422$): A tendency toward higher anxiety levels was observed among adolescents who reported more than 6 hours of daily screen time; however, the association was not statistically significant (Figure 6).

Fig. 4. Physical activity and participation in sections ($p = 0.170$): Light-colored bars represent adolescents who attend sports or dance sections; dark-colored bars represent adolescents who do not attend organized sections

Fig. 5. Psycho-emotional well-being and participation in sections ($p = 0.162$). Light-colored bars indicate adolescents who attend sports or dance sections; dark-colored bars indicate adolescents who do not attend organized sections

Fig. 6. Anxiety level and screen time ($p = 0.422$): Light-colored bars represent adolescents with low anxiety, medium-colored bars represent moderate anxiety, and dark-colored bars represent high anxiety. Screen time is categorized by average daily duration

Anxiety level and number of active hobbies ($p = 0.316$): High anxiety is more common among adolescents with few active hobbies (Fig. 7).

Anxiety level and number of hobbies that are only observed ($p \approx 0.28$): Increased anxiety is more common in the group with a large number of observed hobbies (Fig. 8).

Correlations that were not statistically confirmed ($p > 0.5$)

Anxiety level and psycho-emotional well-being ($p = 0.645$): No clear correlation was found between anxiety levels and emotional well-being. A similar distribution of anxiety was observed within each level of well-being (Fig. 9).

Overall assessment of correlation

All considered correlations were grouped by level of confidence (p-value) and presented in a table with a brief analysis (Table 1). This allows us to visualize the depth and complexity of the results obtained (Fig. 1).

Based on the research conducted on the topic: «The correlation between the level of anxiety and motor and social activity in students aged 14 - 16,» the following was established:

Motor activity has an indirect correlation with the level of anxiety. Students who systematically attend sports or dance classes are more likely to have lower levels of anxiety ($p = 0.018$), higher levels of physical activity ($p = 0.170$), and psycho-emotional well-being ($p = 0.162$).

Hobbies as an indicator of social activity also show some impact on emotional state: fewer active hobbies are associated with increased anxiety ($p = 0.316$);

a large number of **observed but not realized hobbies** is also associated with a higher level of anxiety ($p \approx 0.28$);

students participating in sections demonstrate a wider range of interests ($p = 0.021$).

Digital activity (screen time over 6 hours per day) is associated with higher levels of anxiety, although without statistical significance ($p = 0.422$), indicating an important trend.

Psychoemotional well-being and anxiety do not have a clear correlation within this sample ($p = 0.645$), which indicates the complexity of the adolescent's emotional structure and the need for an individual approach.

Fig. 7. Anxiety level and number of active hobbies ($p = 0.316$): Light-colored bars represent adolescents with low anxiety, medium-colored bars represent moderate anxiety, and dark-colored bars represent high anxiety. The number of active hobbies is categorized by reported frequency

Fig. 8. Level of anxiety and number of hobbies that are only observed ($p \approx 0.28$): Light-colored bars represent adolescents with low anxiety, and dark-colored bars represent adolescents with high anxiety. No respondents with moderate anxiety were identified in the observed hobby categories

Fig. 9. Correlations that were not statistically confirmed ($p > 0.5$): Light-colored bars represent adolescents with low anxiety, medium-colored bars represent moderate anxiety, and dark-colored bars represent high anxiety. Psycho-emotional well-being is categorized according to WHO-5 score groups

Discussion

The results of the study confirm current scientific ideas about the close correlation between physical and social activity and the level of anxiety in adolescence. The established statistically significant correlations (for example, between participation in sports clubs and lower levels of anxiety, $p = 0.018$) are valuable empirical confirmation of the conclusions of international meta-analyses, which demonstrate the positive effect of regular physical activity on reducing anxiety symptoms in adolescents [8].

These work data correlate with the results of a study conducted in China, where it was found that physical exercise indirectly reduces social anxiety through the development of self-efficacy and

a decrease in emotional suppression [13]. Attending the sections in the study can be interpreted as an integrated factor of motor and social activity, since group forms of leisure contribute to both physical activity and inclusion in the team, the formation of supportive correlations, and the reduction of isolation, i.e. factors that have been proven to reduce the level of anxiety [3,5,11].

Another important observation is the correlation between the number of active hobbies and a lower level of anxiety ($p = 0.316$). This is consistent with the findings [6] that multivariate social participation has a positive effect on psycho-emotional well-being and reduces the risks of

developing emotional disorders in adolescents. Participation in hobbies that are actively implemented (and not just through observation) expands the horizon of life views, goals, meanings and reduces focus on anxious thoughts.

A trend towards increased anxiety was also found with excessive screen time (over 6 hours, $p = 0.422$). This is consistent with international data: excessive use of gadgets is often associated with reduced sleep quality, social isolation, and increased anxiety. In particular, UNICEF data (2023) indicate that adolescents who spend more than 4 hours a day online have a 30 - 40% higher level of anxiety than those who adhere to the recommended balance [4].

The context of war deserves special attention. As noted in the work, adolescents in Ukraine experience additional psycho-emotional stress due to danger, loss of stability, and displacement. A study by the Ministry of Health of Ukraine (2024) showed that over 60% of adolescents in areas close to combat operations have symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, or anxiety [17].

In this context, physical activity becomes particularly important as a psychoregulatory mechanism. Psychologists emphasize that regular physical activity helps reduce cortisol levels,

stimulates the production of endorphins, dopamine - which increases emotional stability even in stressful conditions [18]. Also relevant are the results of UNICEF Ukraine (2023): participation in sports and volunteer programs reduced anxiety levels by 27% among displaced adolescents [4]. At the same time, the results of the study did not confirm a statistical correlation between the level of anxiety and psychoemotional well-being ($p = 0.645$). This may be explained by a small sample ($n = 33$) or the influence of external factors, such as academic load, intra-family situation, individual resources. It is worth noting that psychoemotional well-being is a multidimensional construct that is not always linearly related to manifestations of anxiety.

Thus, the results obtained logically fit into modern ideas about the role of physical and social activity as protective factors for the mental health of adolescents. The work confirms the hypothesis that active involvement in active interesting leisure and sectional activities contributes to a decrease in anxiety levels, and can also be used as a preventive tool in conditions of increased stress - in particular, during war.

Conclusions

The level of anxiety in adolescents aged 14-16 is largely related to the extent of their involvement in physical and social activity. Systematic attendance at sections contributes to the formation of a stable emotional background, a wider range of interests, and a decrease in anxiety.

The formation of a culture of leisure and an active lifestyle in adolescents can be an effective preventive measure for maintaining mental health. For further research, it is advisable to involve larger samples and study in more depth not only the quantitative, but also the qualitative characteristics

of physical and social activity. Physical activity forms a stable foundation for the formation of a healthy personality of a teenager. It contributes to the development of physical qualities, strengthening mental health, and improving social adaptation. The formation of positive motivation for an active lifestyle should become one of the main educational tasks. In the face of modern social challenges (in particular, the war in Ukraine), physical activity is becoming even more relevant as a resource for the resilience and vitality of the younger generation.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Received: 2025-11-19

Accepted: 2026-01-121

In press: 2026-01-26

Published: 2026-01-27
